

**Project SOP D-JRP17-
WP4.SOP3 – MALDI-TOF-MS
Workpackage 4**

Responsible Partner: BfR, FLI

Contributing partners: ANSES, APHA, INIAV,
INSA, IZSAM

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	<i>Identification of <u>emerging Brucella</u> species: new threats for human and animals</i>
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP JRP-17 IDEMBRU
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2020
Duration	36 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Project SOP	D-JRP17-WP4.SOP3 - MALDI-TOF-MS
Project Acronym	IDEMBRU
Author	Sascha Al Dahouk, Falk Melzer
Other contributors	Vitomir Djokic, Roland Ashford, Adrian Whatmore, Dirk Hofreuter, Daniela Prasse, Sandra Cavaco, Giuliano Garofolo, Flavio Sacchini, Fabrizio De Massis, Katuscia Zilli, Mihail Milanov, Hristo Daskalov, Ana Cristina Ferreira, Acacia Ferreira Vicente, Guillaume Girault, Luca Freddi, Claire Ponsart
Due month of the report	31 – Decembre 2022
Actual submission month	April 2022
Type <i>R: Document, report DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	<i>OTHER</i> Save date: 26-Apr-23
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default) CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)</i>	PU This is the default setting. If this project deliverable should be confidential, please add justification here (may be assessed by PMT):
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EMA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): Social Media: Other recipient(s):

MALDI-TOF-MS

1. Purpose

These working instructions are used to prepare sample materials for performing MALDI-TOF-MS.

SOP is based on the manufacturer's instructions (Bruker Daltonics GmbH & Co. KG., Bremen, Germany)

2. Reagents, equipment

- Ultra pure water
- Ethanol 99.9%, HPLC grade
- Formic acid 70%, LC-MS
- Matrix solution: 50 µl Trifluoroacetic acid 5.0%, HPLC grade plus 50 µl Acetonitrile 99.98%, Ultra LC-MS plus 1.5 mg Alpha-Cyano-4-hydroxycinnamic acid 99.0%, HPLC grade (vortex for 5 min, centrifuge for 5 min at max rpm, use supernatant as matrix solution)
- Pipettes
- Filter tips, various sizes
- Centrifuge, 13200 rpm
- Teflon flasks
- 96-spot steel plate target
- Falcon tube, 50 ml

3. Procedure

Sample preparation

- a) Some biological material (single colony to full inoculation loop) is taken with a pipette tip or with an inoculation loop and transferred to an Eppendorf tube, into which 300 µl ultra pure water has been added.
- b) Suspend the sample well with an Eppendorf pipette (a slight turbidity should be visible).
- c) By addition of 900 µl ethanol 99.9 % and subsequent careful mixing the proteins are precipitated (*Brucella* spp. are inactivated after this procedure. The sample can be stored at -20°C until further processing.
- d) Ethanol precipitation:
Centrifuge the bacterial suspension in 75% ethanol, pour off the supernatant and discard and centrifuge again briefly at max. speed. Pipette off the supernatant to completely remove the alcohol from the sample.
- d) Allow pellet to dry for approx. 5min. at room temperature.
- e) Add proteins to aqueous solution:
 - Suspend Pellet in 50 µl 70% acetic acid as well as possible with pipette.
 - Add an equal amount of acetonitrile to the sample, vortex and centrifuge for 2 min at maximum speed.
 - Spot 1- 1.5 µl from the clear supernatant onto target plate and allow to dry at room temperature (not under the running safety cabinet!).
- f) Immediately after drying (max. 10 min) the sample is coated with 1- 1.5 µl matrix solution each. Again allowed to dry at room temperature.

g) The samples should be measured as soon as possible (oxidation reaction!).

4. Measuring process/Data acquisition

Please follow instructions for your MALDI-TOF instrument

e.g. microflex LT MALDI-TOF MS system

5. Additional information

Information on how data evaluation should be carried out can be found, for example:

Kornspan D, Brendebach H, Hofreuter D, Mathur S, Blum SE, Fleker M, Bardenstein S, Al Dahouk S. Protein Biomarker Identification for the Discrimination of *Brucella melitensis* Field Isolates From the *Brucella melitensis* Rev.1 Vaccine Strain by MALDI-TOF MS. *Front Microbiol.* 2021 Oct 22;12:712601. doi: 10.3389/fmicb.2021.712601

Guidelines for validating species identifications using MALDI-TOF-MS in a single laboratory or in laboratory networks